

A Study On Vocabulary-Learning Problems Encountered by Non-English Majors at Ho Chi Minh City University Of Food Industry

Tran Ngoc Lam

Email: ngoclam004219@gmail.com

Faculty of Foreign Languages, Ho Chi Minh city University of Food Industry, Vietnam.

Abstract

A study on vocabulary- learning problems encountered by non- English major in HUFU "done on the basis of theory, the results of previous studies and the situation of English learning of students Not specializing in English at HUFU. Vocabulary plays an important role in learning and using English, In learning and practicing language skills such as listening, speaking, reading and writing, vocabulary helps learners understand most of the information transmitted. through reading texts, listening texts, and communicating with others in English. Proficiency and fluency mostly depend on practice, the basic elements are still meaning units such as words, phrases and sentences, and vocabulary is an important component in meaning units. This is a combination of qualitative and quantitative research. The survey of more than 400 students of colleges and universities in 2018 shows that students are aware of the importance of skills in English communication in general and of English vocabulary in particular. However, the reality of student learning does not reflect that. In addition, the results of empirical research show that two proposed design methods vocabulary cards and repetition are proven to be effective and can be applied to all in students.

Keywords: Vocabulary, non- English major, vocabulary card, communication, encountered.

1. Introduction

1.1. Theoretical basis and context of vocabulary learning.

Learning and improving foreign language skills, especially English, is extremely necessary for students because this subject is included in all study programs and is a compulsory condition for students. In other words, the more vocabulary a learner knows, the more likely they will be able to understand the target language. However, as Nation (2001) notes, learning all of the 20,000-25,000 words an average native English speaker knows is not a reasonable goal for most learners, especially with limited time and resources. Students at colleges and universities. TOEIC is applied at HUFU and students must study and pass all the TOEIC English modules needed for their degree, or they must provide an equivalent English proficiency certificate to meet the standard. English output. However, these are only observational data of the individual. To have practical data and sufficient basis to experiment with the method to help students improve their vocabulary and at the same time improve their English ability. In fact, during the TOEIC test for students in the 2017 and 2018 courses at the school, the number of students who scored low and need to learn basic English is very

much: about 400 students in both courses (6 classes for 2017 course, 3 courses for 2018, based on actual number of classes taken) although most students have completed the 7-year English program at high school. In addition, through a preliminary analysis of some of the students' answers to the reading and listening questions, we realize that incorrect answers often fall into questions to test vocabulary. Studies made by O'Malley and Chamot (1986) confirm that most language learning strategies can be used for vocabulary tasks. However, up to now, there has not been any official survey data on the situation of learning vocabulary in particular and learning English in general of HUFU students.

1.2. Purpose of the research.

This study was conducted to fill the gap of lack of research on vocabulary learning strategies in today's context and to supplement students' awareness of the importance of vocabulary learning strategies. It is hoped that the findings from this study will spark learners' interest and allow them to select and use strategies for vocabulary learning that are right for them. Moreover, this study can serve as a guide for those interested in introducing effective vocabulary learning strategies into their classrooms, and it can also help teachers guide learners of. They apply the most effective vocabulary learning strategies possible.

2. Literature review

Over the past 50 years, the science of second language acquisition has had a lot of research around student learning vocabulary of students on a global scale. Most of the research is conducted in the following specific areas: Case-based vocabulary methodology, contextual and non-contextual vocabulary learning. There are many opposing views between Language experts are involved in these two ways of learning vocabulary. There is a lot of compelling evidence that proves that vocabulary based on context (from real documents is much more effective than relying on a list of words already listed (Word list) as Oxford and Scarcella (1994) found in their research, non-contextual vocabulary learning can help students memorize vocabulary for exams and tests, but students will forget those vocabulary words immediately after the exams or tests, and McCarthy (1990) states that if a student learns vocabulary through a meaningful situation, the content clear will memorize and assimilate that vocabulary for a longer time, but most studies like Morgan and Bailey (1943): Wind and Davidson (1969), Gershman (1970). Tudor and Hafiz (1989), Hulstjin (1992) has not yet figured out whether or not vocabulary learning in “favorite situations is effective compared to situations are not excitement for students. However, non-contextual vocabulary learning methods are most used. Researchers have recently attempted to investigate the most commonly used non-contextual vocabulary learning methods, and have found that mechanical methods are more commonly used by students than other methods. The method is highly complex. Cohen and Aphex (1981) observed that students tried to memorize vocabulary they did not know by memorizing. In addition,

O'Mally et al. (1985) also found that repetition method is also used most by students in learning vocabulary. The above-mentioned vocabulary learning methods are considered to be disappointing for researchers and ineffective for students. Ellis (1995) also adding that the "Depth of Processing Hypothesis" (Depth of Processing Hypothesis) when applied to vocabulary learning, Shallow processing only helps students only Stopping at the oral rehearsal level does not help students to stay in memory, but in deep processing, students will approach vocabulary in terms of form and semantic (semantic) and as a result, enhances students' ability to remember and manipulate.

3. Method

3.1. Research question.

In order to investigate the status of vocabulary learning of non-English language students and find out the methods of vocabulary learning, the topic was conducted to find answers to the following three research questions:

1. Student awareness How to learn vocabulary in particular? This research question aims to understand how students perceive and assess the importance of language skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing) along with vocabulary that plays a role in learning and using language. Brother. Questions 1, 2, 3 and 6 in the survey questionnaire were designed to answer this research question.

2. To find out if there is a correlation between students' awareness of the importance of English skills and clumsiness in learning and using English with the amount of time and effort invested to improve their skills and improve vocabulary, the second research question is asked. At what level does a student's learning consciousness affect the situation and attitude of their vocabulary learning ?. Feedback to questions 4 and 5 will be used to answer the research question.

3. One of the important goals of this research is to find ways to learn vocabulary effectively. What vocabulary learning methods might be appropriate for the attitudes and learning styles of non-English language students? Designed based on the characteristics, style and nature of current student learning method. The remaining questions, interview information, together with empirical research to find answers to this research question.

3.2. The object of the research.

The research topic is to investigate the situation and find out ways to improve vocabulary learning of non-English language students at HUFU. They are college and university students of the 2017 and 2018 courses of various disciplines in both social sciences and engineering. The study subjects included 400 randomly selected students. The time of responding to the survey is the subject of studying English TOEIC. This means that all students also attend an English program and this subject has the same characteristic for all students, which is the condition for students to be considered for graduation. Therefore, students may be aware of the importance of this subject at a relatively equal level Dynamic learning is not equally expected because in the course of approaching and studying the subject, the subject rescued many different teachers directly instructed. Depending on the individual requirements and methods of instruction of the teacher, there is more or less the motivation for student learning

between classes. This can also be considered as a factor that has a certain influence on the survey response information.

3.3. Research tools.

3.3.1. Survey questions Based on research questions as well as the theoretical basis of vocabulary learning in general and English vocabulary in particular and based on the results of other studies in the same field of study, the questionnaire consists of 15 questions. The questions revolve around three main issues: student assessment of the importance of vocabulary in English use and learning, the situation of students learning English vocabulary and the nature of vocabulary learning. What methods of vocabulary learning students are using.

3.3.2. Vocabulary list. When participating in the experimental method, students are provided with a TOEIC vocabulary list for each common topic in business communication as well as vocabulary content that students will have to study and be assessed. The vocabulary list can include words students already know and words that students don't know yet. But most of these vocabulary words are new to students. The vocabulary test is also designed primarily using vocabulary in the vocabulary list provided to students.

3.3.3. Vocabulary test. Before taking the experimental section all three groups of students are required to take a vocabulary test. The purpose of this test is to determine the level of vocabulary of each group of students and is also the basis for exchanging students' results through post-test. The test consists of 60 vocabulary multiple choice questions. Each question consists of 4 options and is designed as a sentence completion. The number of vocabulary tested is drawn from the list of vocabulary provided to students. Many of the empirical studies, including the pre- and post-test sections used together with the test and the measured results, still reach a certain level of validity. However, the test used for post-empirical assessment is another version of the pre-empirical test. Still 60 clumsy words were tested as in the pre-empirical test, however the internal of each question was redesigned. Although the time before and after the experiment is 9 weeks apart, it is still possible for students to remember the content of the test they have done before, so renewing the question content is essential.

4. Result

For the most experimental survey question, "How do students perceive English learning in general and vocabulary in particular?", The information from the analytical data shows that the majority of students appreciate the importance of 2 Listening and Speaking skills in learning and using English, and most students are aware of the role and importance of vocabulary in learning and using foreign languages. Background information about learning time in English can be considered as sufficient for students to be aware of skills as well as vocabulary. Survey results show that the majority of students have learned English at high school with a period of 6 years or more (English learning system 7 years) with the rate of 95.7% of the 370 students who answered this question. This confirms that the time students learn English before going to university

is relatively long enough for students to equip themselves with basic and competent English skills at an intermediate level and high class. However, a surprising thing is that 89.5% of these students think that they are not able to use English effectively. This may explain that the previous learning environment (at high school level) of most students did not allow them to use English in and out of class or they did not pay much attention to learning English. . Relevant to the main information needed to answer the first research question - the importance of language skills (listening, speaking, reading, writing) - in using English effectively, most students Survey respondents said speaking and listening skills were more important than other skills. Of the 370 responses to this question, 297 (75.4%) of the respondents considered speaking skills to be important, and a 57.6% rate of speaking and listening was equally important. However, most things underestimate the role of the other two skills: reading comprehension (29.7%) and writing (39.5%). In addition to appreciating the importance of listening and speaking skills, the vast majority of students (92.4%) also found that vocabulary plays an important role in the first-class form that contributes to social communication. English language facilities effectively.

The second research question is, "To what extent does a student's academic consciousness affect their vocabulary situation and attitudes?" Information about the time spent on self-study English and vocabulary self-study in a day of the surveyed students shown in Figure 2 illustrates the second research question as follows: Survey data shows that of the total of 367 questionnaires (33 without answers to this question) about the time spent studying English every day, the number of students studying English less than an hour / days account for a high proportion (69.8%), followed by the study time of 2-3 hours / day (27.2%), the number of students who spend more than hours on learning English is very rare, only accounting for rate of 3.0%. This means that most students invest in learning a foreign language, but the time is relatively modest, which may require time for other subjects or other activities. - With the time spent learning English like that, of course will affect the time spent studying vocabulary. From the statistics of the survey results, it can be seen that about 82% of the students asked spent less than 30 minutes a day to study vocabulary, there are some who never learned vocabulary (4 students themselves) add in the answer sheet when the questionnaire does not provide this option), or rarely or occasionally, or only when needed or free. For the remaining number (18%), the study of words is more focused, students spend a lot of time on vocabulary learning (45 minutes or more), even some people still use words 60 minutes (10 people) to 90 minutes (2 people) to learn vocabulary with the amount of time allocated for learning vocabulary so can also have a certain effect on the number of words that students learn in a day. Specifically, this result confirms that nearly 62% of students learn vocabulary from 3 to 5 words in a day while 6 to 9 words make up only 23% and the remainder are studying more than 10 sheets /day. - In addition, the interview results also show that 17/40 students answered 5-10 words, accounting for 42.5%, 9 students studied 10 or more words, 6 students studied less than 5 words, 4 students students learn more than 10 words, 3 students choose to study 20, 30 and 50 words respectively. In addition, 2 students answered that they did not determine the number of vocabulary each time they should refuse to provide.

5. Discussion

It can be seen that the majority of students appreciate the role and importance of vocabulary in using English in communication. Learning a foreign language in general and learning English in a clean language are a skill-based process that requires students to practice long term. For good speaking skills, students must practice speaking anytime, anywhere, and students must do the same for the remaining three language skills of listening, reading and writing. However, students will encounter many difficulties when practicing skills without the necessary vocabulary. Without vocabulary, students cannot express their ideas when speaking and writing, and cannot understand spoken words and listeners when practicing listening and reading. It can be said that vocabulary is an essential condition in the process of student training to formulate language skills. As a rule of thumb, if students appreciate the role of such vocabulary then of course they will invest a lot. However, research results show a paradox between students' consciousness and actions. In the first research question, most students put the role of skills and especially vocabulary in learning and using English, but invest less time and effort in learning English. He in general and learn vocabulary in particular. The lack of regular vocabulary can explain why the test scores are not so high. This is consistent with the previous research results about the vocabulary and reading comprehension ability of students related directly to each other. This result partly confirms the English proficiency of students through the TOEIC tests.

6. Conclusions

Scientific research project "Study the current situation and propose methods to learn English vocabulary for HUFU English majors" is conducted on the theory and reality of students' general English learning situation. Non-English major at HUFU The survey results show that students are fully aware of the importance of English in general and of English vocabulary in particular. The paradox is quite large, and that also partially explains their TOEIC test results. If it is necessary to reconsider the role of vocabulary in the use of English in communication, the vocabulary is For students who want to communicate well or use English effectively, they need to improve practice (Practice makes perfect) because of the nature of learning a foreign language. General and vocabulary learning in particular are basically the same so the above two vocabulary learning methods should be widely applied to sine foreign language learners like English TOEIC in particular and students learning English in general.

References

- Ahmed, M.O. (1989). Vocabulary Learning Techniques. In P. Meara (Ed.) Words 3-14, London:CILT.
- Brown, C. & Payne, M. E. (1994). Five Essential Steps of Processes in Vocabulary Learning. Paper presented at the TESOL Convention, Baltimore, Md.
- Cohen, A.D. & Aphek, E. (1981). Easifying Second Language Learning. *Sudies in Second Language Acquisition* 3 (2), 221-236.
- Cunningsworth, A. (1995). *Choosing Your Coursebook*. Oxford: Heinemann.
- Ellis, N. (1995). Vocabulary Acquisition: Psychological Perspectives and Pedagogical Implications. *The Language Teacher* 19(2), 12-16.

Gershman, S.J. (1970). Foreign Language Vocabulary Learning under Seven Conditions. Unpublished doctoral thesis, Columbia University, New York.

Hulstijn, J. (1992). Retention of Inferred and Given Word meanings: Experiments in Incidental Vocabulary Learning. In P. Arnaud & H. Béjoint (Eds.), *Vocabulary and Applied Linguistics* 113-125. Basingtoke: Macmillan.

Marcella, H. H., & Paul, N. (2000). Unknown Vocabulary Density and Reading Comprehension. *Reading in a Foreign Language* 13 (1), 403 - 430

McCarthy, M.J. (1990). *Vocabulary*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Ming-Ju. A. H., & Hsin-Yi, L. The Correlation between Vocabulary Knowledge Depth and Reading Comprehension. Master Thesis. Ming Chuan University, Taiwan